

QUIZ**LAST NAME: FORTICH****FIRST NAME: DENNIS****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PR. LAURENT CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on MacOS 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which of the following is the least suggested approach in selecting a research topic?**

- Select topics on the internet based on available online sources¹**
- Select topics that fits into a larger context (historical, social, cultural, functional, economical)
- Select topics that are often misunderstood by people outside the field
- Select topics that are posed by researchers as an unanswered question at the end of the article

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 18–20.

2. **Which of the following is considered a good academic essay?**
- An essay that intends to present its argumentation based on closely related points by reasoning and evidence²**
 - An essay that details the topic's description, concept, and interpretation
 - An essay that provides examples based on available sources online
 - An essay that expresses own author's feelings about the topic
3. **Which is the best approach is creating a working hypothesis?**
- Find a research question, develop the topic, create hypotheses, select the working hypothesis
 - Find a topic, develop assumptions, find the research question, create hypothesis
 - Find a topic, develop the topic, question the topic, create assumptions
 - Find a topic, question the topic, evaluate the question, answer the question, select the best answer³**
4. **How to sequentially establish a research argument based on a working hypothesis?**
- Develop research claim, provide evidences, align evidences with working hypothesis, establish relevance of evidences to hypothesis
 - Provide a reason for the working hypothesis, provide evidences for such reason, acknowledge opposing viewpoints, establish the relevance of the reason⁴**

² ACA-401D EUCLID University LMS, "Essay Writing: The Basics," n.d., 2, accessed June 7, 2019, <http://www.lc.unsw.edu.au>.

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition*, 21.

⁴ Ibid., 37–40.

- Establish the context, restate working hypothesis, provide the significance of the question, provide assumptions
 - Analyze the working hypotheses, provide evidence, support with reason, provide assumptions
5. **What would be the structural organization of final introduction and conclusion?**
- A topic is introduced with a context, question, significance, and brief claim; and conclude with detailed claim, new significance, and further research application or question⁵**
 - A topic is introduced with a research question, its significance, context and brief claim; and conclude with detailed claim, new significance, and further application or question
 - A topic is introduced with a research question, argumentation, significance, and opposing viewpoints; and conclude with detailed claim, new significance, and further application or question
 - A topic is introduced with a context, question, significance, and brief claim; and conclude with claim, new significance, and warrant
6. **When should review of literature be referred?**
- Before asking questions and data collection
 - At various stages of dissertation process⁶**
 - During concept development
 - After data collection and data analysis

⁵ Ibid., 70.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 74.

7. **What are the steps in constructing a well-developed literature review?**

- Retrieve, sort, organize, and develop research design
- Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, Control
- Identify, analyze, synthesize, and develop conceptual framework⁷**
- Code, sort, theme, and generalize

8. **What would be the structural organization of a literature review?**

- Statement of purpose, research question, rationale, process, conceptual framework, summary
- Statement of purpose, topics, claim, evidence, review, conceptual framework, summary
- Statement of purpose, topics, rationale, process, review, conceptual framework, summary and implications⁸**
- Statement of purpose, problem, claim, process, review, concept, summary and implications

9. **Which of the following approach is least likely to improve methodical validity?**

- Employ methodical redundancy in data collection
- Include combination of quantitative instruments in conjunction with qualitative methods to provide corroboration of evidence
- Adopting the methodical approach of related literatures⁹**

⁷ Ibid., 76.

⁸ Ibid., 85.

⁹ Ibid., 95.

- Use of triangulation concept to clarify meaning through multiple perception

10. How are potential biases controlled in the design, implementation, and analysis?

- By ensuring interrelationship between purpose, conceptual framework, research question, and methods
- Transparency of methods including detailed account on how all the data were analyzed and interpreted
- By providing an in-depth detailed description that provide basis for a qualitative account's claim to relevance in some broader context
- All of the above**¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

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¹⁰ Ibid., 108–109.